

Error analysis of day-ahead PV production multi-step forecasting with chained regressors

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Abstract—This paper presents a comprehensive error analysis of the day-ahead photovoltaic (PV) production multi-step forecasting model that uses a chained support vector regression (SVR). A principal component analysis (PCA) is also implemented to investigate possible improvements of the SVR prediction accuracy. Special attention was given to the hyper-parameter tuning of the chained SVR and PCA+SVR models; specifically, the dispersion of the prediction errors when fine-tuning the model with an experimental halving random search algorithm implemented within `scikit-learn` as `HalvingRandomSearchCV` (HRSCV). The obtained results were compared with the traditional randomized search technique, `RandomizedSearchCV` (RSCV). The chained SVR model prediction errors were analysed for several different parameter distribution settings. After doing repetitive fine-tuning and predictions, it was observed that the HRSCV tends to choose sub-optimal hyper-parameters for certain scenarios, as will be elaborated in the paper. Moreover, when analysing prediction errors of the same model fine-tuned repetitively with the HRSCV and RSCV, it was found that HRSCV creates larger errors and more inconsistency (variability) in the prediction results. The introduction of the PCA to the chained SVR model, at the same time, reduces the influence of exogenous variables and, on average, increases its performance and decreases prediction errors.

Keywords—support vector regression, chained regression, principal component analysis, hyper-parameter tuning, successive halving, hyperband

I. INTRODUCTION

The photovoltaic (PV) production forecasts are becoming increasingly important as the share of the PV production in the global electricity production increases rapidly. The intermittent nature of power produced by PV plants creates numerous challenges related to the power system reserves planning and prospective PV plant revenues on the electricity market. Therefore, accurate PV production forecasts are important to both grid operators and plant owners.

The PV production forecast horizon spans from very short term (typically ranging up to 1 minute) to long-term (typically 1-10 years), with the most common being the 24 hours ahead of the next day [1]. There are a wide variety of PV production forecast methods, categorized as statistical, physical, and hybrid methods. According to [2], about 70 % of the recent studies employed statistical methods. Support vector regression (SVR) and neural networks are the most widely used statistical methods for the PV power predictions [3]. In

recent literature on the PV production forecasts, most of the papers implemented the deep-learning neural networks, including feed-forward neural network [4], recurrent neural network (RNN) [5], RNN with long short-term memory (LSTM) [6], and hybrid LSTM-CNN (convolutional neural network) [7], to name a few.

Many of the prediction models utilize weather data in the PV production forecasts. However, some authors also opted for machine-learning PV prediction models that do not use weather data. For example, in [8], the authors implemented a day-ahead PV forecasting model with information gained only from the historical PV power. The authors argue that models without exogenous inputs could be used during periods of weather service system malfunction and in cases where weather data could become too expensive to purchase. Their model also performs better than the simple persistence technique for different forecast horizons. Other PV power prediction forecasts without external weather data include, e.g., [3], [9].

This paper presents a day-ahead multi-step forecasting model using the chained support vector regression without utilizing the forecasted weather data. The predictions are made firstly with historical PV production data and additionally engineered features, and secondly with weather data fully excluded from the model training. A principal component analysis (PCA) is used in conjunction with the chained regression to investigate the possible prediction performance improvements. The main focus of this paper is not on the increase of the accuracy of the existing PV production forecast methods, nor on creating machine learning models that compete with the complex data-driven deep-learning neural networks. Instead, the attention is more focused on the hyper-parameter tuning of the chained SVR model and the examination of the successive halving tuning technique [10].

The paper is organized as follows. Section II introduces a dataset used for the model evaluation. Section III gives a brief theory of the SVR and PCA, along with hyper-parameter tuning techniques used throughout the paper. A test case is given in section IV, where a multi-step prediction model with chained regression and PCA is applied to the dataset. Different hyper-parameter settings and tuning techniques are tested and the model's prediction errors are examined. Finally, conclusions are given in section V.

II. DATASET DESCRIPTION

Liege microgrid open data used for scientific paper [11] is utilized in this paper. The dataset is accessible via Kaggle platform¹. It is composed of 15-minute weather forecast data, 5-second monitored PV production and consumption of the microgrid, and 15-minute resolution PV and consumption weather based forecasts. For the purpose of this paper, only 15-minute weather data and 5-second monitored PV production data has been utilized.

The weather data is composed of irradiance, temperature, wind speed, relative humidity, precipitations, snow height and cloud levels. The data spans from May-10th to June-18th, 2019, while the PV production data spans from May-13th to June-20th of 2019. Snow data was dropped from the weather data since it was not observed during the available data span.

Five second PV production data was first smoothed using the Kaiser filter with a window shape parameter $\beta = 8.6$. After filtering, data is resampled to 1-hour resolution using the rolling mean method. Filtering the data before resampling will contribute to the increased model generalization in a later phase of the training period. Original and filtered 5-second PV production data (before resampling) is shown in Fig. 1.

Filtered PV production time-series, along with the histogram, autocorrelation (ACF), and partial autocorrelation (PACF) of the PV production are shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1. Original and filtered PV production data with Kaiser filter

The following features are extracted from the dataset: (1) 24-hour time lags, (2) First-hour and 24-hour difference, (3) Rolling mean and max of 1-hour shifted PV production, (4) Hour of the day and month indicators, and (5) One-hot encoding of sunshine hours.

Weather data features related to the hour-ahead forecast are removed. A total of 283 features was created, out of which 250 features are related to historical weather data. Model training is performed in two scenarios: (1) Using the full-featured dataset with historical weather data and (2) Reduced features dataset without the weather data.

The data is split into training (53%), validation (27%), and test (20%) sets, resulting in 445, 222, and 167 data points in

¹<https://www.kaggle.com/jonathandumas/liege-microgrid-open-data>

Fig. 2. PV production time-series statistical properties

training, validation and test sets, respectively. Shuffling of the data is not utilized since the seasonal effect is not embedded into the provided data (i.e. the data spans only approx. 35 days). Otherwise, the data shuffling could prevent the possible lack of model generalization in situations where training is done during one season and testing during another [3].

III. MULTI-STEP FORECASTING

A. Support Vector Regression

Given the training data, the SVR is finding a fitting function (i.e. hyperplane) that deviates from the target labels below the value specified with an error sensitivity parameter ϵ . The fitting flexibility is introduced with slack variables ξ and ξ^* , allowing deviations beyond ϵ , but with an added penalty. The SVR is formulated as the convex optimization problem, represented with the Eqs. (1) and (2). The objective function is to minimize the ℓ_2 norm of the fitting function coefficient vector with the added penalty, and the maximum allowable deviations from the target labels are handled within the constraints. Provided with training vectors of features $x_i \in \mathbb{R}^m$ and labels $y_i \in \mathbb{R}^n$, the solution of the following optimization problem are the coefficient vector $\omega \in \mathbb{R}^m$ and intercept $b \in \mathbb{R}$:

$$\min \frac{1}{2} \|\omega\|^2 + C \sum_{i=1}^n (\xi_i + \xi_i^*) \quad (1)$$

subject to constraints:

$$\begin{aligned}
y_i - w^T \phi(x_i) + b &\leq \epsilon + \xi_i \\
w^T \phi(x_i) + b - y_i &\geq \epsilon + \xi_i^* \\
\xi_i, \xi_i^* &\geq 0, \quad i = 1, \dots, n
\end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

Here, the $\|\omega\|^2 = w^T w$ is the ℓ_2 norm of the coefficient vector. The regularization parameter C controls the strength of the penalty added to the objective function. The non-linear function ϕ maps the training feature vectors x_i into the higher dimensional space to perform linear regression. Since the transformation to a higher dimensional space can be computationally expensive, different kernel functions are used to carry out this task more efficiently. The `scikit-learn` library offers linear, polynomial, radial basis function (RBF) and sigmoid kernel functions, with the possibility to define custom kernels. In this paper, RBF kernel is implemented:

$$K(x_i, x_j) = \exp(-\gamma \|x_i, x_j\|^2) \tag{3}$$

where γ is a coefficient parameter of the RBF kernel function.

For a more thorough description of the SVR, and for the solution to the optimization problem posed by (1), interested reader is referred to consult [12].

B. Principal Component Analysis

The Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is also performed on the data and used in conjunction with chained SVR in order to test if the combined PCA+SVR model can perform more accurately than chained SVR alone.

The PCA is a data transformation technique for extracting relevant information from datasets. The main idea behind PCA is to reduce the number of features to a smaller subset of features which retain maximum variance. Interested reader is at this point advised to refer to the [13] for more details about the PCA.

C. Chained regressors

A single SVR model has no native multi-output support and can predict a single numerical value. There are many ways of doing multi-output predictions with the SVR. In this paper, chained regression is used, where the labels are predicted sequentially based on the information gained from the previous predictions. In other words, the SVR models are ordered in a chain, where i -th model is trained based on the available features and predictions of the previous $i - 1$ models. Given the information from the previous predictions, the model is able to exploit correlations between the labels.

Two models are formed: (1) The chained SVR model and (2) The PCA in combination with the chained SVR, designated as PCA+SVR.

D. Hyper-parameters optimization

1) *Tuning techniques*: Model's hyper-parameters are fine-tuned using randomized search and successive halving random search with cross-validation (CV), implemented in `scikit-learn` under the names `RandomizedSearchCV`

(`RSCV`) and `HalvingRandomSearchCV` (`HRSCV`), respectively.

The randomized search evaluates the model performance by selecting the random combination of the hyper-parameter values at each iteration from the specified distributions [14]. The outcome of the fine-tuning process is the random combination of hyper-parameters that resulted in the most favorable score. Fine-tuning hyper-parameters with randomized search can be a time-consuming process.

Various algorithms are used to increase computational speed and allocate resources more efficiently. In this paper, we used a successive halving search technique proposed in [15]. In the first iteration, the algorithm evaluates performance on a given number of hyper-parameter combinations (initially specified), using a relatively small training sample, and eliminates half of the parameter combinations (hence halving) with the lowest score. As the number of parameter combinations is reduced, in each successive iteration the algorithm increases the training sample size and keeps evaluating and halving until a single configuration remains.

The main problem with the successive halving algorithm is that the number of parameter combinations must be specified initially. If the number of combinations specified is relatively low, the last iteration will not utilize a full training sample. In the opposite case, when the number is relatively high, many parameter combinations will be scored with a large training samples and thus significantly decrease the computational speed.

To cope with this problem, authors in [10] proposed a novel Bandit-based algorithm that chooses the number of parameter combinations N in such a way that the last iteration uses as many samples as possible. The algorithm, named Hyperband, performs a grid search over the N and calls the successive halving algorithm in the background for each N . The authors showed that the Hyperband algorithm is 5-30 times faster than a popular Bayesian optimization algorithm on different deep-learning and kernel-based problems.

The number of parameter combinations is automatically selected within HRSCV using the Hyperband algorithm. The important parameter for HRSCV is the so-called halving parameter, which defines the proportion of parameter combinations eliminated in the subsequent iterations. The value of 2 is used throughout this paper.

2) *Model hyper-parameters*: The SVR with the RBF kernel has three hyper-parameters: regularization parameter C , the error sensitivity parameter ϵ , and the kernel coefficient parameter γ .

The regularization parameter C adjusts the tolerance on the error sensitivity. The higher the value of parameter C , the more penalty is added to the optimization function for errors outside the margin, and thus, the model tends to make a better fit on the training data. This also makes it more difficult to solve the underlying optimization problem [16]. Contrary, small values of the regularization parameter tolerate more errors (values outside of the margin ϵ). The kernel coefficient parameter is

related to the influence of the individual training samples. In general, large values of γ tend to capture complex data shapes, but with possible overfitting problems.

The SVR parameters C and ϵ are searched over log-uniform (Log-U) distribution, defined by the following equation:

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{x \cdot \log(\frac{b}{a})}, \quad a \leq x \leq b, \quad b > a > 0 \quad (4)$$

where a and b are shape parameters of Log-U distribution. For coefficient parameter γ of the RBF kernel, a different configuration where used. Initially, it is searched over the two possible values: $\gamma = 1/(n \cdot \sigma^2)$ or $\gamma = 1/n$, where n in the number of features and the σ^2 is the variance of the training samples. Afterward, γ is searched within Log-U distribution.

An additional model generality is included by adding the possibility of standardizing features (removing mean and scaling variance to unit value) in the preprocessing phase. By applying the model tuning technique, the model will automatically choose whether or not to standardize the features (hereinafter the term StandardScaler will be used interchangeably) based on the cross-validation score.

The number of principal components needs to be defined for the PCA in advance. The higher the number of kept components, the more information is contained in the training data; however, possible unnecessary training features will not be eliminated. The number of principal components to keep is specified with a floating-point number $0 < m < 1$, where m represents the percentage of the minimum amount of variance that needs to be explained by the retained components. A continuous uniform distribution between 0 and 1 is used for the search of the number of components. While projecting the data, each component is scaled to unit variance.

For the PCA+SVR model, the hyper-parameter tuning of the PCA is performed in combination with chained SVR, so that the optimal performance of the combined estimator is achieved.

IV. TEST CASE

In this chapter, multi-step prediction models are applied to the Liege microgrid dataset. Both full-feature and the reduced datasets are used for model training. Within each multi-step model, a walk-forward multi-step prediction methodology is used, where predictions are made 24-hour ahead each time the model walks forward by one hour. For each prediction interval, features up to the 1-hour lag are given to the model as input. Up to 72 walk hours are used for model predictions.

HRSCV is primarily used for hyper-parameter search because of its computational speed advantage. For RSCV, a total of 100 parameter settings (samples) are used for fine-tuning.

A detailed error analysis of fine-tuned models is provided only for the chained SVR model when using historical weather data. In all performed predictions, the chained SVR regularization parameter C and error sensitivity parameter ϵ are searched over Log-U distribution with shape parameters $a = 10^0$, $b = 10^3$ for C and $a = 10^{-5}$, $b = 10^{-2}$ for ϵ .

Fig. 3. Characteristic prediction error results when tuning hyper-parameters of the chained SVR model with HRSCV

The model performance is measured by means of normalized root mean squared error (NRMSE) metric.

A. Results

Fig. 3 shows characteristic prediction error results of the chained SVR model with two different configurations of parameter distributions. The hyper-parameter γ is searched over two possible values (see legend in Fig. 3). In the first configuration, the StandardScaler is optional, while in the second configuration, StandardScaler is excluded from the search. The tuning of hyper-parameters is performed with the HRSCV.

Fig. 4 shows the prediction error results, for each iteration, when repetitively fine-tuning hyper-parameters of the chained SVR model with HRSCV and RSCV. With each model tuning

Fig. 4. Dispersion of prediction error results when tuning chained SVR model 100 times repetitively with HRSCV and RSCV. The SVR hyper-parameter γ is searched over Log-U distribution with shape parameters $a = 10^{-4}$ and $b = 10^0$

technique, 100 iterations of predictions (for each walk hour) with fine-tuned hyper-parameters are performed. This time third configuration setting is used, where γ is fine-tuned over the Log-U distribution with the shape parameters $a = 10^{-4}$ and $b = 10^0$.

The performance of the Chained SVR model, without weather data, is depicted in Fig. 5. The hyper-parameters of the same model are tuned iteratively 10 times with both RSCV and HRSCV. Prediction errors for 10 iterations are represented with the middle line corresponding to the average NRMSE and lower/upper dashed lines corresponding to the NRMSE deviations measured as two standard deviations from the average.

In Fig. 6, the NRMSE of the chained SVR and PCA+SVR model's predictions are compared with utilized historical weather data. The model's hyper-parameters are fine-tuned with HRSCV. Prediction errors correspond to the cases when $\gamma = 1/(n \cdot \sigma^2)$, without feature standardization in the pre-processing phase.

B. Discussion

The chained SVR model is fine-tuned using the three different configurations of parameter distributions. As mentioned,

the search space of the regularization parameters C and ϵ is kept constant throughout the test case.

In the first parameter configuration setting, the RBF kernel parameter γ search is limited among two values, $\gamma = 1/n$ or $\gamma = 1/(n \cdot \sigma^2)$. The data standardization is optional, i.e. the model tuning technique will choose whether to apply it or not. When the process of fine-tuning chained SVR model with HRSCV and predicting is repeated 100 times, in 91/100 iterations the model is optimally tuned and resulted in a prediction error represented by the green line in Fig. 3. The fine-tuned value of γ is $1/(n \cdot \sigma^2)$, without feature standardization. The remaining 9/100 predictions led to different hyper-parameter configurations with inferior prediction performance compared to the other 91 scenarios. The NRMSE of these predictions is depicted by the orange line in Fig. 3. For all 9 scenarios, it was observed that the features were standardized and the chosen value of the RBF kernel parameter is $\gamma = 1/n$.

In the second configuration, the feature standardization is not performed and it was removed from the search space. All other hyper-parameter distributions remained the same. After performing again 100 scenarios, it was observed that in 96/100 scenarios the model was optimally tuned and the underlying

Fig. 5. Chained SVR model prediction errors while tuning the hyper-parameters with RSCV and HRSCV without utilizing weather data

Fig. 6. Chained SVR and PCA+SVR models performance comparison.

prediction errors are represented again with the green line on Fig. 3. However, in 4/100 scenarios the γ parameter was chosen to be $1/n$, which resulted in the prediction errors represented by the red line on Fig. 3. Obviously, the HRSCV was not able to find optimum hyper-parameters for the chained SVR model.

In contrast, when tuning hyper-parameters of the same model for previous configurations with RSCV, the prediction errors were consistent and resulted in a green line on Fig. 3. However, the RSCV hyper-parameter tuning was performed not more than 20 times on previous parameter configurations.

For the third parameter configuration, the Log-U distribution with shape parameters $a = 10^{-4}$ and $b = 10^0$ is used for the RBF parameter search. The model was fine-tuned with both HRSCV and RSCV, 100 times repetitively. From the results shown in Fig. 4, it can be seen that the prediction error results, when tuning hyper-parameters with HRSCV, are both heavily scattered (i.e. high variance) and, in general, inferior compared to the results obtained when fine-tuning with RSCV.

As noted before, the previous results were obtained only when using an extended dataset with historical weather data features. If the weather data is completely removed from the features, a relatively small dataset with only 33 features remains. The model fine-tuning is only performed for the first parameter configuration setting, i.e. feature standardization is optional and $\gamma = 1/n$ or $\gamma = 1/(n \cdot \sigma^2)$.

When repetitively tuning and predicting on the chained SVR model without historical weather data features, an increased prediction error variance is observed with HRSCV compared to the RSCV. This can be seen on Fig. 5. In general, while tuning hyper-parameters with RSCV, NRMSE is staying inside the limits of two standard deviations for the same model tuned with HRSCV. Interestingly, when tuning with HRSCV, the dispersion of the results is observed, but significant deviations from the mean scenario were not captured.

The results presented in Fig. 6 show the differences between chained SVR and PCA+SVR models with historical weather data features. The model predictions with PCA+SVR in 10 successive iterations show on average smaller NRMSE and higher variance. Additionally, when comparing Fig. 5 and 6, it can be seen that the PCA+SVR model with weather data features performs similarly to the chained SVR model without weather data features. Therefore, PCA is effectively eliminating unnecessary weather data features.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a chained SVR and PCA+SVR multi-step day-ahead forecasting models of the PV production implemented within the `scikit-learn`. The chained SVR model is exhaustively tested with HRSCV on the extended dataset with 283 features and different parameter distribution settings. The results show that for the first parameter distribution setting the selected parameters in 9/100 scenarios are considerably different and inferior compared to the remaining optimally tuned scenarios, while in the second parameter distribution setting in 4/100 scenarios the selected parameters resulted

in substantially worse prediction NRMSE. When comparing HRSCV and RSCV for the third parameter distribution setting, the model predictions when fine-tuning hyper-parameters with the RSCV show favorable performance due to lower NRMSE and more consistency in successive iterations. In contrast, the significant NRMSE deviations from the mean scenario were not captured when fine-tuning the model without historical weather data. The PCA+SVR model performs similarly to the chained SVR model without weather data, directing us to the conclusion that historical weather data has no significant influence on the model performance.

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